

Ideological and artistic features of folk singing

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Abstract: The role and importance of folk music in the development of the art of singing; The role of the teachings of Eastern thinkers in the development of the art of singing; It was discussed about the organization of the features of the tradition of teacher and discipleship in the art of national singing; it is important to study the ideological and artistic features of Uzbek folk singing.

Key words: Folk art, folk songs, musical perception, national values, customs and traditions, morals, virtue, national education.

Using its artistic and educational possibilities by referring to samples of our folk music heritage in school music culture classes is one of the main factors of increasing the effectiveness of the lesson. The state policy in the field of personnel training implemented in our country envisages the formation of a thinking, free-thinking person through a continuous education system aimed at educating the young generation intellectually and morally. One of the important conditions for achieving efficiency in modern education is to clearly define the content of education at each stage, the compatibility of the curriculum with the student's programs, the level of mastery of students and regular checking of the result of education. Each specific subject has its own psychological features and conditions for acquiring knowledge, and students' ability and interest in this subject has a positive effect on the outcome of the work. In this case, there is a great need for special subject pedagogical technologies. One of the psychological features of improving lesson efficiency in music education is the development of intellectual thinking - musical perception by creating an emotional state. Understanding the artistic content of music, fully feeling the experiences expressed in it is realized only through perception with emotional awareness.

Examples of folk music have great potential in developing artistic thinking and musical perception in young students. It is the basis of education of our youth in the spirit of national values, customs and traditions, and it is of great importance to use its attractive, unique tones as a means of spiritual and aesthetic education. The great thinkers of the East, Farobi, Ibn Sina, Rudaki, and Zamakhshari, wrote down valuable ideas about educating a person, cleaning his soul and mind from dust through the art of music. Fakhridin Razi (13th century) writes about this in the encyclopedia "Collection of Sciences". "If it sounds in harmony with high and low sounds, it matches the feelings of the heart. Differences in sounds and tones express different emotional feelings. With its power, it gives peace and pleasure, the unchanging state of sound extension can never be pleasant, if it acts on the basis of certain laws, the listener begins to like it." While different characteristics of sounds create different moods, low and high tones are appropriate. If it evokes sadness, it is because of the combination of high sounds with low sounds.

Wrath, anger, and thought are expressed by low sounds, feelings-emotional actions by high sounds. Especially during the renaissance period, the theoretical foundations of Uzbek and Central Asian folk music in general were perfected in the scientific treatises of scholars such as Ibn Sina, Safiddin Urmawi, Mahmud ash-Sherazi, Abdulkadir Maroghi, Abdurrahman Jami, and Zainolubiddin Husayni. This was made possible by the stable social situation in the time of Sahibqiran Amir Temur and the Timurids, and the efforts of the wise sahibqiran in the direction of the development of science, culture and enlightenment. The musical-theoretical and artistic-

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aesthetic views of the musicologists and musicians who worked in this period were reflected in the music treatises of the XIV-XVI centuries. Examples of these are Zaynolobuddin Husayni's "Kanuni ilmiki wa amali muzik" ("Scientific and practical laws of music"), Muhammad Nishopuri's "Book about the science of music", Ahmadi's "Discussion of Music", Najmuddin Kavkabi Bukhari's "Risolai muzik" and "Risala dar bayani duvazda". maqom" ("Treatise on twelve statuses") can be cited. The theoretical and practical issues of folk music, its social importance and important educational tool are expressed in these scientific treatises. The historical development of folk music shows that in different periods it has developed as the main tool of the social life of our people and served as an important factor in educating the young generation.

The song genre forms the basis of folk music, as it is widely expressed as a song of the social life, national life, customs and traditions of the people. In the performance of the song, musical tones and poetic content combine and have a strong emotional impact on the listener.

Music is more popular than other genres due to its wide range of visual possibilities and unique impact. In folk songs, humanity - patriotism, internationalism, honesty, tolerance, generosity, loyalty to the motherland, purity of heart and other human qualities are glorified in their own way. negative situations - ruthlessness, lying, indifference, stinginess, laziness, vanity and other characteristics are condemned. This creates an opportunity for the formation of positive character traits and spiritual and moral education in students and young people through folk songs. One of the requirements for the successful implementation of the new educational model of music culture is the main factor in the realization of the potential forces that serve the development of our society by focusing on the essence rather than the form. Today, students and young people are less interested in listening to folk songs and playing national musical instruments. Because they, as listeners, are more interested in modern pop songs. However, not all of the music created and performed in this genre is of high demand. And we don't always mean that music is a tool of strong emotional influence.

Local styles play an important role in ensuring the richness, attractiveness and variety of folk songs. Fergana-Tashkent, Bukhara-Samarkand, as a result of their veneration by our people, Uzbek folk music preserves its ancient roots. For example, in the Fergana valley, there is great singing and yallachilik, in Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya oasis, epic poetry, in Samarkand and Bukhara regions, there is more folklore and folk songs and the diversity of music, in the singing of Khorezm, there is a unique intensity and enthusiasm, Turkmen and edges similar to the melodies of Azerbaijani music are noticeable. Epics are told in the form of speech-declamation in other regions of Uzbekistan, but in Khorezm they are sung in their own forms. Each way and method of performance in Uzbekistan is closely related to the roots of the national heritage of the people, and at the same time, they have preserved some of their own characteristics and distinctive aspects. This leads to the development of folk music. In order to perform the folk songs in a figurative and emotional way, it depends first of all on the conscious penetration of the students into the musical and poetic world of the song. In this case, it is necessary to direct the students' attention to working with the musical text of the song as much as possible, and try to find the most characteristic means of expression in it according to the content of the song. Beautiful, clear and correctly pronounced words create positive emotions in students and the performer himself. Another characteristic of children's emotions is that they are related to specific circumstances. That is, the emotional experience that occurs in children occurs in one or another concrete situation. Accordingly, creating conditions and situations that interest, attract, and excite students is an important condition

for developing musical perception in them. Of course, folk songs are distinguished by the expressiveness and simplicity of the melody, the brightness of the rhythmic form, the originality of the poetic text, because modern Uzbek musical works were created on the basis of our deep-rooted national music. Understanding the importance and content of modern musical works created on the basis of folk music leads to the development of students' thinking and perception, as well as to drawing individual conclusions about this sample of music.

Creating problematic situations in the lesson is a leading method, and it creates favorable conditions for them to express their views and attitudes through debates and discussions. Through this method of education, the attention span of students expands and becomes voluntary. As the well-known scientist Ye. V. Nazaykentsky said: "any piece of music is accepted on the basis of a concrete life reserve, including musical ideas, skills, and habits. The main reason for emphasizing the song genre in school music education and upbringing is that the novelty of musical melodies and poetic text has a complex impact on the child's emotional and artistic-creative thinking and creates adequate imaginative connections. . Acquired skills of imagination and imagination help the formation and development of musical perception. Studying the creation of folk songs in the lesson, first of all, attention is paid to the art of singing as a form of general artistic culture, and secondly, to imagine and study the social and spiritual characteristics of our nation, national values and our musical culture. is to educate a positive attitude to history. Our people's unique way of life, thinking and worldview are national songs, musical and spiritual wealth, which are an expression of attitude to life and reality. Art masterpieces such as "Shashmaqom", "Alpomish", the life path of our national heroes such as Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Spitamen, Amir Temur are examples for young people. Our national music, which has been improving and developing over the centuries, calling our people to goodness, has all the possibilities for the spiritual education of the youth of our free and prosperous republic, which is building its future. It is the main duty of specialists in the field to develop musical perception and thinking in students and young people by realizing these opportunities.

List of used literature.

1. Akbarov I.A. Musiqa lug'ati. Toshkent G'.G'ulom nomidagi adabiyot va san'at nashriyoti 1987 yil
2. Karamatov F.M. "O'zbek xalq musiqa merosi" XXasrda I-kitob .Toshkent G'.G'ulom nomidagi adabiyot va san'at nashriyoti. 1978 yil
3. Komil Ochil. Qaldirg'ochni ko'ndirgan qo'shiq . "Zarafshon" Samarqand 1993
4. Amonullayev "Darslikka xalq merosini o'rganish". Boshlang'ich ta'lim 1993
5. Sarimsoqov B."O'zbek merosi va folklori. Toshkent "Fan" 1986 yil
6. Mirzayev T. va boshqalar. O'zbek folklor ocherklari . Toshkent "Fan" 1998 yil
7. Абдуллаев К. Ф., Умурова М. Ё. ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ УРОКА ПЕНИЯ В НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ШКОЛЕ //CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICAL THEORY AND COMPUTER SCIENCES. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 66-69.
8. Umurova M. Y. Educational Significance of Children's Folklore Songs //AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND LEARNING FOR DEVELOPMENT. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 148-152.
9. Umurova M. Y. Formation of Patriotic Feeling in Youth Students through Folk Songs //Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 99-103.

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10. Yorievna, U. M. R., & Karimovna, N. N. (2020). Innovative approach to the development of musical abilities in children with disabilities health opportunities. *Проблемы педагогики*, (2 (47)), 40-41.

11. Yoshiyevna U. M. THE ROLE OF THE CREATIVE HERITAGE OF EASTERN THINKERS IN THE FORMATION OF THE SPIRITUAL AND MORAL OUTLOOK AND MUSICAL PERCEPTION OF YOUNG PEOPLE //E-Conference Globe. – 2021. – С. 102-104.

12. Yoshiyevna U. M. The emergence and stages of development of navruz //Herald pedagogiki. Nauka i Praktyka. – С. 8.

